

5 المؤتمر العلمي

لدراسات وأبحاث الاقتصاد و العلوم الإدارية

الأبحاث المقبولة في

المؤتمر العلمي الخامس لدراسات وأبحاث الاقتصاد والعلوم الادارية
كلية الاقتصاد والادارة - جامعة الملك عبدالعزيز
١٤٤١هـ - ٢٠٢٠م

الجزء الأول

The Fifth Scientific Conference on Economics and
Managerial Studies
Faculty of Economics & Administration, King Abdulaziz
University
1441 - 2020

Volume 1

Business process improvement framework analysis and comparison

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Abstract

The use of process reference models increases the efficiency and effectiveness of process management. Furthermore, the use of appropriate process reference models that are adapted to company-specific requirements can help tremendously. In practice though, few organizations operate in only one industry and process reference models are not a perfect fit for most organizations. In addition, most frameworks like the PCF outline *what* an organization does. However, there are function-specific frameworks which also outline *how* work occurs in terms of additional lower-level activities and tasks, as in the SCOR model. To resolve this issue, an integrated framework is developed for the PCF and SCOR models and an application method is suggested in this paper. The framework would be an advantageous tool for firms that plan to implement the aforementioned models as well as managing and improving business processes.

Keywords: PCF, SCOR, Process reference models, BPM

Introduction

The use of process reference models increases the efficiency and effectiveness of process management. Specifically, the use of appropriate process reference models that are adapted to company-specific requirements can help tremendously [1].

Few organizations operate in only one industry and process reference models are not a perfect fit for most organizations [2,3]. In addition, most frameworks like the APQC Process Classification Framework (hereafter PCF) outline *what* an organization does. However, many function-specific frameworks also outline *how* work occurs as additional lower-level activities and tasks like the Supply Chain Operations Reference model (hereafter SCOR) [4,5]. Therefore, there is a need to integrate the two types of models, which can be done by structuring the functional area based on the PCF framework. Next, it would be beneficial to build out the more detailed process elements based on the SCOR.

Firms want all the advantages of different process reference models that contribute to process improvement in multimodal environments [6].

The evolution of process reference models has stabilized two main frameworks widely known as the PCF and SCOR models. These two models are prevalent and are two of the most important worldwide [6,7].

There is a scarcity of research analysis in comparing these two models and thus introducing a unified framework.

The purpose of this paper, therefore, is to investigate how the functional processes defined in these two models are related, i.e. what PCF functional processes are detailed and defined by each SCOR functional process and how the resulting integrated framework can be applied.

To this extent, three objectives are accomplished in this study. First, each of the aforementioned models is analyzed separately. Second, the components of the two models are unified and thus an integrated framework is developed. Third, an application method is suggested. These accomplishments provide a solution that allows us to deal with the limitations noted above.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section Two reviews the relevant literature. The methodology is introduced in Section Three. In Section Four, the PCF is first analyzed. Then, the SCOR model is introduced and examined. Next, the two models are compared in terms of their features and characteristics. Following this, the integrated processes framework is developed. Finally, an application method is presented.

Literature review

The process reference models are developed by a range of practitioners, non-profit and government bodies, and academia. They can be defined as generic conceptual models that formalize recommended practices for a special domain and serve as a foundation for process identification, definition, assessment and improvement [8,9,10]. Examples of best-known process reference models are the Supply Chain Operations Reference Model (SCOR) by APICS and the Process Classification Framework (PCF) by the American Productivity and Quality Center (APQC).

Using process reference models provides several benefits [1,7]. For example, process reference models may be useful for checking the completeness of the processes identified by an organization. Moreover, they provide a standardized vocabulary that is useful for labeling processes. As a result, one obvious benefit is that they enable benchmarking. In addition, they can serve as a starting point for developing a classification of major process areas.

Although firms should choose the process reference model moremost suitable to their main goal, it can still be beneficial to adopt the advantages of other models.

The possibility of viewing the real functional processes in the firm from different perspectives (generic and specific, for example) is an important but complicated task.

Thus, comparing and mapping these different process reference models is needed for both academics and practitioners.

Only a few researches have focused on the two studied process reference models [e.g., 4,11] compared to studies that have focused on other process reference models [e.g.,12,13,14]. None of these studies have compared the two targeted process reference models in this paper.

For instance, Jalote (1999) proposed a way for transitioning from ISO 9001:1994 to SW-CMM level 4, based on an actual organization's transitioning experience. He pointed out that a simple mapping between ISO 9001:1994 and SW-CMM is not helpful to field staff. Furthermore, it is useful to describe what additional actions must be accomplished for a typical ISO 9001-compliant organization that is transitioning to SW-CMM.

Furthermore, Yoon et al.2015)) proposed a standard R&D process model that can be applied to various R&D projects. Then this model was compared with traditional process models, namely the Capability Maturity Model Integration, European Industrial Research Management Association, and ISO15288. In

addition, they suggested an assessment method to evaluate an R&D process. Their results present 21 R&D processes and the best practices of each process, enabling a company to find and improve weak R&D processes.

In addition, Mantje et al. (2016) performed case studies at two of the hospital's clinics to both identify differences between the clinics' supporting processes as well as to validate the efficacy of the APQC-HPCF. Their results showed that the clinics performed nearly all of the prescribed processes. Deviation from the APQC-HPCF is mainly explained by the fact that some of its contents are designed for the American market and do not apply to the Dutch market. The clinics also performed some additional supporting processes that are not present in the framework. Also, minor differences in supporting processes between the two clinics were found. The results show that the efficacy of the APQC-HPCF is validated by a large extent but cannot be proven completely.

Methodology

To accomplish the research objectives, first, a content analysis is carried out and the relevant literature is researched using the Google Scholar, Web of Science, and ProQuest databases as well as other relevant sources such as the APQA and Supply Chain Council websites. This is conducted using appropriate keywords as well as inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Next, the targeted models are analyzed and the integrated framework is developed. The results and the detailed proposed analysis are shown in the following sections.

Analysis and Results

In this section, the PCF is analyzed first before the SCOR model is introduced and investigated. Next, the two models are compared in terms of their features and characteristics. Following this, the integrated processes framework is developed. Finally, an application method is presented.

The Process Classification Framework (PCF)

The American Productivity and Quality Center (APQC) has developed a comprehensive taxonomy of generic processes applicable in many industries (PCF) to make comparisons and present contrasting views on processes across different industries [15]. The APQC updated the generic model and also introduced adaptations for specific industries such as: automotive, banking, broadcasting, consumer products, education, electric utilities, pharmaceuticals and retail. Too few studies have focused on analyzing the PCF framework [e.g., 4,11]. The APQC framework is structured in five hierarchical levels: category, process group, process, activity, and task, [15], see Figure 1.

Figure 1. PCF levels
Sources: [15]

“Category” is the highest level of process in the firm. The PCF then divided this level into two groups: operating and management processes, comprising 13 enterprise level categories (Table 1).

Table 1. Level 1 of the PCF Framework

Category	
Operating Processes	
1	Develop Vision and Strategy
2	Develop and Manage Products and Services
3	Market and Sell Products and Services
4	Deliver Physical Products
5	Deliver Services
Management and Supporting Services	
6	Manage Customer Service
7	Develop and Manage Human Capital
8	Manage Information Technology (IT)
9	Manage Financial Resources
10	Acquire, Construct, and Manage Assets
11	Manage Enterprise Risk, Compliance, Remediation, and Resiliency
12	Manage External Relationships
13	Develop and Manage Business Capabilities

Sources: [15]

Operating processes are reflected by Develop Vision and Strategy, Develop and Manage Products and Services, Market and Sell Products and Services, Deliver physical Products, deliver service and Manage Customer Service. Whereas management and support Services are embedded by Develop and Manage Human Capital, Manage Information Technology, Manage Financial Resources, Acquire, Construct, and Manage assets, Manage enterprise risk, compliance, and resiliency, Manage External Relationships, and develop and manage business capabilities. “Process Group” is the next level, representing a group of processes. Examples of this level are performing sales repairs and developing sales strategies. Process is the third level, composed of a process group. An example of this level is *performing internal analysis* of the process group, *defining the business concept and long-term vision*. This level generally comprises key elements required to accomplish the process. “Activity” is the next level, showing core events that are executed when performing a process (the preceding level). An example of this level is *analyzing organizational characteristics* under the process *performing an internal analysis*. “Task” is the next level within the PCF framework of activities. This level may differ widely based on contexts and industries and is generally more fine-grained. An example of this level is *creating a business case and obtaining funding and design recognition and reward approaches*. The focus of this paper is the first level: category (Table 1).

SCOR framework

SCOR is a framework created by the Supply Chain Council. The model is organized around five high level processes: Plan, Source, Make, Deliver and Return and has variations for particular types and styles of supply chains. The SCOR model has been developed to describe business activities related to all phases of satisfying a customer’s demand. The model itself contains several sections and is organized around the five primary management processes of Plan, Source, Make, Deliver and Return (shown in Figure 2). The model defines core processes and management and support processes and provides precisely defined performance measures for each process [16,17].

Figure (2) SCOR structure
Sources: [16,17]

These processes span: all customer interactions (order entry through paid invoice), all physical material transactions (supplier's supplier to customer's customer, including equipment, supplies, spare parts, bulk product, software, etc.) and all market interactions (from the understanding of aggregate demand to the fulfilment of each order).

	Level		Examples	Comments
	#	Description		
Within scope of SCOR Process Types (Scope)	Plan, Source, Make, Deliver, Return and Enable	Level-1 defines scope and content of a supply chain. At level-1 the basis-of-competition performance targets for a supply chain are set.		
	2	 Process Categories (Configuration)	Make-to-Stock, Make-to-Order, Engineer-to-Order, Defective Products, MRO Products, Excess Products	Level-2 defines the operations strategy. At level-2 the process capabilities for a supply chain are set. (Make-to-Stock, Make-to-Order)
	3	 Process Elements (Steps)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schedule Deliveries Receive Product Verify Product Transfer Product Authorize Payment 	Level-3 defines the configuration of individual processes. At level-3 the ability to execute is set. At level-3 the focus is on the right: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Processes Inputs and Outputs Process performance Practices Technology capabilities Skills of staff
Not in scope Activities (Implementation)	Industry-, company-, location- and/or technology specific steps	Level-4 describes the activities performed within the supply chain. Companies implement industry-, company-, and/or location-specific processes and practices to achieve required performance		

Figure (3) The SCOR: three levels of process boundaries
Sources: [16,17]

As presented in Figure 3, the model is designed and maintained to support the supply chain in various complexities and across multiple industries. The model focuses on three process levels and does not attempt to describe the details of process implementation (level 4) required for performing level 3 processes (the industry specific activities). Therefore, organizations that adopt supply chain

improvements using the SCOR framework will extend the model with specific processes [16,17]. Examples of level 4 processes for the electronics industry are: print pick lists and pick items.

In addition to the five level-1 management processes (Plan(P), Source(S), Make(M), Deliver(D), Return(R)) that form the structure of the SCOR model, each level 2 process can be categorized as one of three process types in the model: planning, execution and enable.

A planning element is a process that aligns expected resources to meet expected demand requirements. The planning processes balance aggregated demand across a consistent planning horizon. Planning processes generally occur at regular intervals and can contribute to supply chain response time.

Execution processes are triggered by planned or actual demand that changes the state of material goods. They include scheduling and sequencing, transforming materials and services, moving products to the next process, and can contribute to the order fulfilment cycle time.

Enable processes prepare, maintain, or manage information or relationships upon which planning and execution processes rely.

As indicated in Figure 3, the model has three levels. Level 1 is the supply chain. Level 2 consists of the high-level processes that make up a supply chain, including Source, Make, Deliver and Return. Plan is an additional SCOR process that describes management planning. These Level 2 processes are first defined, and then their variation is specified, before being categorized into a set of Level 3 subprocesses [18]. For example, P1.4 is a notation that indicates a third level process element. In this case, it is a Plan (P – level 1) element that is concerned with supply chain planning (1 – level 2) and is specific to establishing and communicating supply chain plans (4 – level 3).

SCOR defines five generic performance attributes (reliability, responsiveness, flexibility, cost, and efficiency) and three levels of measures that analysts can use. Figure 4, below, depicts how a supply chain process can be measured. In the case of m0 measures, we measure the performance of the organization as a whole and attribute to it the overall effectiveness of the supply chain. In the case of m1 measures, we measure the performance of the supply chain as a whole. (SCOR refers to m0 measures as Internal Facing Measures and to m1 as Customer Facing Measures.) M2 measures check on the performance of one of the Level 2 processes, while m3 measures check on the performance of specific sub-processes within a Level 2 process.

Figure 4. SCOR's levels of measures
Source: [16,17]

The models comparison and the integrated framework

To compare the PCF and SCOR models, they are first analyzed based on their features. This is conducted based on the recommendations from Kirchmer and Fettke et al., with some modifications. They suggested criteria for characterizing process reference models. These criteria include identification, general characteristics, structure, and application [1,9]. Table 2 presents this comparison. Next, the two models are mapped in terms of their content (processes).

Since the PCF model is broader in its coverage and the SCOR model is an industry-specific model, it would be easier for organizations if SCOR could be interpreted as an expanded form of PCF.

The developed framework is organized as shown in Table 3, showing the contents of the framework: a combination of the PCF (with a focus on level 1 processes) and any correspondence of SCOR components.

Because it is important to understand and apply the developed framework in a practical manner and to avoid likely subjectivity in interpreting the process definitions, it is suggested that the mapping be accompanied by an explanation derived from the respective models. Given the limited amount of space available here, Table 4 highlights an example of an explanation column.

Table 2. Comparison of the models

Identification		General characteristics				Structure				
No	Name	Primary resource	Origin	Responsibility for modeling	access	Tool support	Domain differentiation	Domain description	Process modeling language	Modeling framework
1	PCF	[15]	Practice	The American Productivity and Quality Center	open	No	Function	Cross industry-business process management	Graphical and verbal	Yes
2	SCOR	[16,17]	practice	The Supply Chain Council	Limited	Yes	Function	Supply chain management	Graphical and verbal	Yes

Source: Author's creation based on [15,16,17]

Table 2. Comparison of the models

No	Name	Structure				Application	
		Availability of metrics	Construction method	Include definitions	Structured step of diagnosis or audit	Reuse and customization	Use case
1	PCF	yes	Similar to data flow diagram	S	No	Specification/Adaptation	multiple
2	SCOR	Partly	Similar to data flow diagram	M	Yes	Training and Certification	multiple

S—strong match; M—medium match; W—weak match.

Source: Author's creation based on [15,16,17]

Table 3. Structure of the integrated framework

PCF	SCOR
1 Develop Vision and Strategy	1. Plan 6. Enable (sE7. manage supply chain network), (sE10. manage supply chain procurement)
2.0 Develop and Manage Products and Services	1. Plan 2. Source 6. Enable (sE2. Manage supply chain performance)
3.0 Market and Sell Products and Services	
4.0 Deliver Physical Products	1. Plan 2. Source 3. Make 4. Deliver 5. Return 6. Enable (sE6. Manage supply chain contracts)
5.0 Deliver Services	
6.0 Manage Customer Service	
7.0 Develop and Manage Human Capital	6. Enable (sE4. Manage supply chain human resources)
8.0 Manage Information Technology (IT)	6. Enable (sE3. Manage supply chain data and information)
9.0 Manage Financial Resources	2. Source 4. Deliver
10.0 Acquire, Construct, and Manage Assets	6. Enable (sE5. Manage supply chain assets)
11.0 Manage Enterprise Risk, Compliance, Remediation, and Resiliency	6. Enable (sE8. Manage supply chain regularity compliance), (sE9. Manage supply chain risk)
12.0 Manage External Relationships	
13.0 Develop and Manage Business Capabilities	6. Enable (sE1. Manage supply chain business rules)

Source: Author's creation based on [15,16,17]

Table 4. Example of the detailed integrated framework

PCF	SCOR	Explanation	Metrics	Practices	Workflow
1	Develop Vision and Strategy	1. Plan This process can be further described as shown below. The Plan processes describe the planning activities associated with operating a supply chain. This includes gathering customer requirements, collecting information on available resources, and balancing requirements and resources to determine planned capabilities and resource gaps. This is followed by identifying the actions required to correct any gaps. For example, this process can be described by its sub-processes and its operations: sP1 Plan Supply Chain The development and establishment of courses of action over specified time periods that represent a projected appropriation of supply chain resources to meet supply chain requirements for the longest time fence constraints of supply resources.	RS. 1.1 RS 3.98 CO 2.001 CO. 3.001 CO. 3.002 CO. 3.003 CO. 3.004 AM. 1.2 AM. 1.3	e.g., BP.018 BP.013 BP.016 BP.019 BP.020 BP.021 BP.024 BP.026 BP.027	

sP1.1: Identify, Prioritize, and Aggregate Supply Chain Requirements

sP1.2: Identify, Prioritize, and Aggregate Supply Chain Resources

sP1.3: Balance Supply Chain Resources with Supply Chain Requirements

sP1.4: Establish and Communicate Supply Chain Plans

sP2 Plan Source
sP3 Plan Make
sP4 Plan Deliver
sP5 Plan Return

Source: Author's creation based on [15,16,17]

Tips for applying the integrated framework

The developed framework can be applied based on the following steps: 1. Provide expertise on process management (including that relating to SCOR) and preferably the owners of the firm's process framework. 2. Have the firm accurately evaluate the process status. 3. Structure the functional area based on the PCF, providing first insights for the definition of appropriate process boundaries, and then map the PCF and firm-specific characteristics needs. 4. Build out the more detailed process elements based on the SCOR as connected in the integrated framework. 5. Check alignment and completeness. The integrated framework includes SCOR processes that are inserted in an appropriate position. However, because of the possibility that some other SCOR processes may cover parts of PCF processes, this needs to be considered.

Discussion and Conclusions

Few organizations operate in only one industry and process reference models are not a perfect fit for most organizations. In addition, most frameworks like the PCF outline *what* an organization does. However, many function-specific frameworks also outline *how* work occurs as additional lower-level activities and tasks. Therefore, there is a need to integrate the two types of models, which can be done by structuring the functional area based on the PCF framework. Next, it would be beneficial to build out the more detailed process elements based on the SCOR.

The purpose of this research is to fill this gap via comparing PCF and SCOR models, developing an integrated framework based on PCF and SCOR models, and proposing an application method.

The findings can be summarized as follows:

Frist. An integrated framework is constructed, based on the PCF and SCOR models.

Second. The results of comparing the two models and the developed integrated framework provide many advantages: (a) to reach and cover broader contents of functional and functional-specific processes within enterprise, (b) to apply to more contexts and industries than for each single model, (c) to provide better identification of best practices concerning core, management, and supporting processes in general as well as supply chain processes in particular, (d) to easily apply the two widely and prominent models in an integrated manner.

Third. The application method for the framework is developed which integrates the two models.

These contributions are not fully elaborated in either of the compared models. Thus, this paper provides a significant contribution to business process management literature and practice.

Further research could be oriented to: (1) linking the developed framework with business process maturity models, (2) conducting empirical investigation of the developed model, and (3) investigating different process reference models in a comparative analysis.

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